

The Mechanism of Photosensitisation and Photo-inhibition from the Point of View of Absorption Spectra.

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The phenomenon of photosensitisation has now been observed in numerous reactions by different investigators. Winther and co-workers (*Z. Wiss. Photochem.*, 1922, **21**, 168; 1913, **13**, 89), Sanyal and Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1923, **128**, 212) and others have shown that the decomposition of Fehling's solution, cupric ammonium-oxalate, Eder's mixture, a mixture of mercuric chloride and tartrate, etc., can be accelerated by ferric or uranyl salts under the influence of sunlight. A mixture of mercuric chloride and ammonium oxalate is almost insensitive to the light of a tungsten-filament lamp but it can be made sensitive to this light in presence of rosin.

Baur and co-workers (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1918, **1**, 186; 1924, **7**, 910; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, October, 1925, p. 629), Bhattacharya and Dhar (*this Journal*, 1927, **4**, 299), and others have shown that zinc oxide behaves as a very powerful sensitiser for numerous photochemical reactions.

Bäckström (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 1460), in a recent communication, observes that benzophenone and acetophenone act as sensitisers for the photochemical oxidation of benzaldehyde and heptaldehyde. Though a large number of sensitisers have come to light yet the mechanism involved in the process of sensitisation is not clearly understood.

Recently Baur and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) have introduced a theory according to which the main reacting constituent is supposed to be polarised in presence of the sensitisers. Some authors are of opinion that the sensitising substance combines with the reacting materials to form an intermediate compound. Sufficient experimental data are not however available for testing the correctness of either of these suggestions. Recently Ghosh and Mitra (*this Journal*, 1927, **4**, 353; 1928, **5**, 191) have measured the increased absorption of light consequent on the addition of uranyl and ferric salts to several organic acids.

The object of the present paper is to elucidate the mechanism of sensitisation and inhibition on the basis of spectral evidence. For this purpose the absorption spectra of the various constituents of a reacting system as well as of the sensitising or the inhibiting substance have been photographed. It is evident from these photographs that the amount of light absorbed by the reacting system changes markedly in presence of a sensitiser.

The following reactions have been investigated from the viewpoint of photo-sensitisation :—

- (i) Reduction of Fehling's solution in presence of uranyl nitrate and ferric chloride.
- (ii) Oxalic acid and chromic acid in presence of manganous sulphate and sulphuric acid.
- (iii) Copper sulphate and potassium oxalate in presence of uranyl nitrate and ferric chloride.

The following reactions have been studied from the point of view of inhibition :—

- (i) Formic acid and chromic acid in presence of manganous sulphate.
- (ii) Oxidation of benzaldehyde in presence of hydroquinone.
- (iii) Oxidation of benzaldehyde in presence of phenol.

The photographs were obtained with an Adam-Hilger Quartz Spectrograph (E 1 type) and Ilford Panchromatic plates were used throughout. An automatic copper arc (220 volts, 4.5 amp.) was used as the source of light. The absorbing substances were placed in rectangular neutral-tinted glass vessels having optically plane parallel ends.

As all the changes studied in this paper take place in ordinary sunlight it is desirable to restrict for the present the limits of the absorption spectra to the visible region of the spectrum. The spectrograph was set for the " first region " of the spectrum, that is, the region where photographs are obtainable within the limits λ 8000-3000Å. The emission spectrum of copper was taken as the comparison spectrum. Though panchromatic plates were used yet no sharp lines beyond λ 6162Å could be obtained towards the infra-red region. Between λ 5700-5200Å no prominent line of copper is noticeable.

The following photographs have been obtained :—

Plate I (from top downwards).

- (i) $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ —N/20 and Fehling's solution.
- (ii) $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ —N/20.
- (iii) FeCl_3 —N/20 and Fehling's solution.
- (iv) FeCl_3 —N/20.
- (v) Fehling's solution.

Plate II.

- (i) MnSO_4 —N/280, $(\text{COOH})_2$ —N/200 and chromic acid—N/440.
- (ii) Oxalic acid—N/200.
- (iii) Chromic acid—N/440.
- (iv) Manganous sulphate—N/280.

Plate III.

- (i) FeCl_3 —N/25 and potassium oxalate—2N.
- (ii) CuSO_4 —N/35, $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ —2N and FeCl_3 —N/25.
- (iii) $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ —N/25.
- (iv) CuSO_4 —N/35, $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ —2N and $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ —N/25.
- (v) Potassium oxalate—2N.
- (vi) Copper sulphate—N/35.
- (vii) CuSO_4 —N/35 and $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ —2N.
- (viii) Copper arc.

Plate IV.

- (i) Chromic acid—N/350, formic acid—N/150 and MnSO_4 —N/400.
- (ii) HCOOH —N/150.
- (iii) Manganous sulphate—N/400.
- (iv) Chromic acid—N/350.
- (v) Copper arc.

Plate V.

- (i) Copper arc.
- (ii) Hydroquinone in ethyl alcohol and benzaldehyde.
- (iii) Benzaldehyde in ethyl alcohol.
- (iv) Hydroquinone in ethyl alcohol.

Plate VI.

- (i) Copper arc.
- (ii) Phenol and benzaldehyde (both dissolved in ethyl alcohol).
- (iii) Benzaldehyde in alcohol.
- (iv) Phenol in alcohol.

It may be noted from the accompanying photographs that in the cases of photo-sensitisation there is always an increase in the absorption of light in presence of the photosensitiser. In fact the absorption spectra of the reacting mixtures in presence of the photo-sensitisers are almost identical with the spectra of the sensitisers themselves.

We have shown in a previous paper (Dhar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 707) that though manganous sulphate acts as an accelerator in the case of the oxidation of oxalic acid by chromic acid yet it acts as a retarder in the reaction between formic acid and chromic acid. Similarly, phenol and hydroquinone act as inhibitors in the oxidation of benzaldehyde.

It will be seen from these photographs that in the case of photo-inhibitors, the absorption spectra of the reacting mixtures remain the same as that of the chief photoactive constituent. As regards the absorption spectrum of the mixture, formic acid and chromic acid in presence of $MnSO_4$, it may be pointed out that the spectral lines are identical with those obtained for chromic acid. In the cases of the oxidation of benzaldehyde in presence of hydroquinone and phenol it is evident that the absorption spectra of the mixtures, benzaldehyde-hydroquinone and benzaldehyde-phenol are similar to the absorption spectra of benzaldehyde which shows marked absorption in the visible region.

From the photographs it is evident that acceleration in light is always accompanied by an increased absorption of light.

The addition of uranium or iron salts to numerous mixtures reacting photochemically causes an increase in the absorption of light by the entire reacting system. Hence both uranium and iron salts act generally as photosensitisers. This increased absorption of light consequent on the addition of iron and uranyl salts has been reported as "exaltation" of the original reacting materials by Ghosh and Mitra (*loc. cit.*) in the cases of certain organic acids.

In the case of photo-inhibitors no such increase in absorption is noted. The spectra of the reacting substances remain practically unaffected by the presence of the non-reactive constituents.

We are trying to prove that substances which are chemically reactive show more marked absorption than substances which are not reactive. An alcoholic solution of benzaldehyde takes up

oxygen more readily than a solution of acetaldehyde, and the benzaldehyde solution shows more absorption than an acetaldehyde solution. Moreover, we have shown that the velocity of the reaction between ethyl alcohol and bromine is greater than that between methyl alcohol and bromine. According to Spring (*Bull. Acad. Belg.*, 1896, 31. 246) ethyl alcohol shows more absorption than methyl alcohol. Hence we believe that chemical reactivity and capacity for absorption of radiations go hand in hand and the results are in support of the radiation hypothesis of chemical change.

Further work in this line is in progress in these laboratories.

Summary.

(1) Absorption spectra have been photographed using a quartz spectrograph of high dispersion of several mixtures containing uranyl nitrate and ferric chloride as photo-catalysts. The photographs show that in presence of uranium and iron salts there is marked increase of absorption of light and these two substances are well known for their photosensitising power.

(2) The addition of manganous sulphate to a mixture of oxalic acid and chromic acid markedly increases the absorption of light by the mixture, and we have proved that manganous sulphate is a marked positive catalyst for the above reaction.

Manganous sulphate acts as a negative catalyst in the reaction between formic acid and chromic acid and it does not cause an increase of the absorption of light when added to the mixture.

(3) Hydroquinone and phenol when added to benzaldehyde retards the oxidation of benzaldehyde and do not increase the absorption of light.

(4) It appears that photosensitivity and increase of absorption of light are closely associated.

PLATE I.

6162
6059
5782
5700

5218
5153
5106

4651
4587
4481

4275

4179

4063
4022

3860

PLATE II.

6182
6059

5782
5700

5218
5153
5106

4651

4587

4181

4275

4178

4063
4022

3860

3687

3635

PLATE III.

PLATE IV.

PLATE V.

8162
6059
5782
5700

5218
5153
5106

4651

4587

4481

4275

4178

4063
4022

3860

3687

3635

PLATE VI.

6162
6059

5782
5700

5218
5153
5105

4651

4587

4481

4275

4178

4063
4022

3860

3687
3635

3530

3381

